

Exploring Deep Reinforcement Learning for Reactive Collision Avoidance

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Abstract— In this extended abstract, we introduce our previously published work [1]. Semi-autonomous capabilities in Micro Aerial Vehicles (MAVs) are crucial for assisting teleoperation and avoiding collisions. We present an approach where operators provide a simple speed and direction command to the MAV. The drone executes the instruction by exploiting a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) model that processes RGB images and the current robot position to follow the command while avoiding collisions. We demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in simulated environments and compare it against a state-of-the-art baseline.

Index Terms—teleoperation, MAVs, DRL model

I. INTRODUCTION

Teleoperating MAVs in obstacle-rich environments poses important challenges [2]. For tasks like surveillance and exploration, human operators face several difficulties when trying to remotely control an MAV, since they cannot perceive effectively the obstacles surrounding the robot and are not able to timely react to possible collisions. To address this, we propose a simplified teleoperation approach. Operators specify direction and velocity, leaving MAVs to follow trajectories while avoiding collisions autonomously.

In the setting considered in this work, we assume that the remote operator sends a command encoding the desired direction and speed, which is then converted to a straight trajectory originating from the initial drone position within the global reference frame, rather than the drone’s local body frame. Hence, when the MAV avoids obstacles, it deviates from the requested trajectory and, therefore, it is necessary to compute commands to allow the robot to realign its position with that of the requested path. (Figure 1). Hence, the MAV needs two fundamental abilities: *Collision Avoidance (CA)* [3] and *Trajectory Following (TF)*.

For this purpose, differently from modular solutions, we introduce a novel end-to-end solution based on DRL [4]. The strategy we propose is monocular, can be adapted to various environments and velocities, and requires only image inputs and drone pose information. In addition, we do not constrain the MAV to fly at a fixed height.

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Fig. 1: Overview of our approach. Our solution tracks the requested trajectory by the operator while avoiding collisions.

The proposed solution is validated in different simulated scenarios, comparing it with a state-of-the-art baseline and studying the generalization performance with respect to environments that differ from the training ones.

II. METHODOLOGY

We start by defining the teleoperation scenario considered. At time t_0 , an operator sends a velocity command to the MAV, defining a 3D straight trajectory. Our objective is to avoid collisions while tracking the requested trajectory, *i.e.*, we seek to minimize the deviation between the current position of the MAV and its corresponding requested position at each time step. We assume that the robot has access only to RGB images and to pose information.

To design the controller that solves the aforementioned task, we exploit the deep reinforcement learning (DRL) paradigm, which trains an agent by interacting with an environment and optimizing the model in order to maximize a task-dependent reward. Since multiple interactions with the environment are necessary, we train the DRL agent in simulation. We formulate the RL problem by defining the following elements:

Action: At each time step, the agent selects a control command $\mathbf{u}(t_i)$. In particular, it computes a 3D jerk vector to control the MAV.

Observations: The environment provides an RGB image and a vector containing MAV pose information. This is encoded in the observation tuple $\mathbf{o}(t_i)$.

Reward: The reward function encourages trajectory tracking and obstacle avoidance. The episode’s termination conditions depend on the occurrence of collisions, high tracking error, or maximum time constraints.

We employ an Actor-Critic framework for our DRL approach. Both the actor and the critic networks are fed with the image processed by a pretrained ResNet CNN [5], concatenated with the MAV pose information; this concatenation is then provided to two fully connected blocks that share the same structure but have different parameters. Optimization utilizes the Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) framework [6] and it takes approximately 32 hours to converge on an Nvidia GTX Titan XP GPU.

The training procedure is performed by taking advantage of the Unreal Engine (UE4) simulator¹, which allows us to create realistic scenarios and safely train the DRL controller. In particular, for the optimization, we design a 3D indoor corridor by randomizing its objects, *i.e.*, at each episode we change their type, texture, position, rotation, and size.

At test time, the actor network acts as the MAV controller, processing $\mathbf{o}(t_i)$ to compute the control command $\mathbf{u}(t_i)$.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To the best of our knowledge, there are no SotA approaches that consider an MAV teleoperation setting presented in this study. Hence, we choose to compare it against a modular strategy that exploits Artificial Potential Fields (APF). We refer to this baseline as APF-CATF.

To assess the generalization performance of our approach, we consider three categories of test environments: the **training-like** environments (TL1-TL4) are corridors resembling training settings; the **training-unlike** environments (TU1-TU4) consist of corridors with varying textures and objects; the **outdoor** settings include a football pitch (FP) and a playground (PG) with obstacles. All the scenarios have been designed with Unreal Engine 4 as for the training ones.

Each experiments start by initializing the MAV in a hovering condition. Afterwards, the operator send a command $\mathbf{v}_d = [v_{d,x} \ 0 \ 0]^T$, used to initialize the trajectory $\mathbf{t}_r(t)$.

Performance comparison metrics are averaged over $N_{tr} = 10$ trials. Trials introduce randomness through MAV’s initial position and jerk noise. Below we provide the metric descriptions:

SR (Success Rate): measures the trial success percentage.

S-DOD (Success-weighted Deviation from Optimal Displacement): computes the MAV’s mean displacement from the optimal path connecting the starting point and the last one at the episode end via the Dijkstra algorithm.

ACE (Average Control Effort): represents the mean control effort integrated over the episode duration.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The quantitative scores achieved in test environments are reported in Table I. Their analysis highlights that our approach outperforms the baseline in the majority of the scenarios against both SR and S-DOD metrics. This is remarkable considering that APF-CATF has a significant advantage over our strategy since it employs error-free (ideal) ground truth

Scenario	APF-CATF			Ours		
	SR	S-DOD	ACE	SR	S-DOD	ACE
TL1	0.2	0.04	11.96	1.0	0.12	4.52
TL2	0.7	0.11	5.81	1.0	0.14	5.39
TL3	0.2	0.03	9.98	1.0	0.26	5.83
TL4	0.9	0.22	2.45	0.6	0.06	5.33
TU1	1.0	0.16	1.81	0.7	0.09	6.09
TU2	0.0	0.00	5.25	0.9	0.08	5.98
TU3	0.3	0.03	7.94	0.7	0.09	5.96
TU4	0.2	0.03	8.56	0.5	0.04	7.14
FP	0.9	0.04	2.02	0.9	0.01	6.15
PG	0.1	0.01	9.69	0.9	0.03	6.54

TABLE I: Quantitative comparison between APF-CATF and our method. Green cells indicate higher metric value.

depth maps instead of raw RGB images. The SR difference between the two methods can be ascribed to an inherent limitation of APF strategies: the repulsive obstacle fields and the "attraction" force exerted by the trajectory tracking task can possibly generate local minima, which causes the MAV to get stuck.

Table I also provides interesting insights about the generalization capabilities of our approach. As expected, the best performances have been achieved in the TL scenarios. Nonetheless, the performance drop on the TU and outdoor environments (not used to train the model) is limited and, in most of the cases, our strategy still outperforms the baseline. Notably, the SR metric in the outdoor scenario is close to 1 (its maximum value), which is noteworthy considering that these environments are very different from the training ones.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a novel teleoperation system that relies on a monocular DRL approach. The proposed approach enables the MAV to accurately follow trajectories while avoiding collisions. Through simulations, we have observed better performance compared to a SotA baseline model. In our future research, we will investigate recurrent networks to address temporal dependencies and perform real-world scenario testing.

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